

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11388436>

TRIGONOMETRIK FUNKSIYALARNING BA'ZI XOSSALARI

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada trigonometrik ba'zi funksiyalarni birini ikkinchisi orqali ifodalsh, trigonometrik formulalarning ba'zi isbotlari va trigonometrik funksiyalarga oid namunaviy masalalar keltirilib o'tilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** trigonometrik funksiya, ayniy shakl almashtirishlar, keltirish formulalari, ikkilangan burchak tushunchasi.*

Maktab matematika kursida trigonometrik ifodalarning juda ko'p ayniy almashtirishlari mavjud bo'lib quyidagilar o'rganiladi.

- Trigonometrik funksiyalarni birini ikkinchisi orqali ifodalovchi ayniy almashtirishlar.
- Trigonometrik ifodalarni soddalashtirishdagi ayniy almashtirishlar.
- Trigonometrik ayniyatlarni hisoblashdagi ayniy almashtirishlar.
- Trigonometrik tenglamalarning yechimini topishdagi ayniy almashtirishlar.

Quyidagi formulalarga e'tibor qarataylik.

Keltirish formulalari:

1. $\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \pm \alpha\right) = \cos\alpha$
2. $\sin(\pi \pm \alpha) = \mp \cos\alpha$
3. $\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \pm \alpha\right) = \mp \sin\alpha$
4. $\cos(\pi \pm \alpha) = -\cos\alpha$
5. $\sin\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} \pm \alpha\right) = -\cos\alpha$

$$6. \cos\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} \pm \alpha\right) = \mp \sin \alpha$$

$$7. \operatorname{tg}\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \pm \alpha\right) = \mp \operatorname{ctg} \alpha$$

$$8. \operatorname{ctg}\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \pm \alpha\right) = \mp \operatorname{tg} \alpha$$

Asosiy trigonometrik ayniyatlar:

$$1. \cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha = 1$$

Isboti: Ushbu asosiy ayniyatni isbotlashda Pifagor teoremasidan foydalanamiz.

$$2. \operatorname{tg} \alpha = \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha}$$

$$3. \operatorname{ctg} \alpha = \frac{\cos \alpha}{\sin \alpha}$$

$$4. \operatorname{ctg} \alpha \cdot \operatorname{tg} \alpha = 1$$

$$5. \frac{1}{\cos^2 \alpha} = 1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha$$

$$6. \frac{1}{\sin^2 \alpha} = 1 + \operatorname{ctg}^2 \alpha$$

Ikki burchak yig'indi va ayirmasining trigonometrik funksiyasi:

$$1. \sin(\alpha \pm \beta) = \sin \alpha \cos \beta \pm \cos \alpha \sin \beta$$

$$2. \cos(\alpha \pm \beta) = \cos \alpha \cos \beta \mp \sin \alpha \sin \beta$$

$$3. \operatorname{tg}(\alpha + \beta) = \frac{\sin(\alpha + \beta)}{\cos(\alpha + \beta)} = \frac{\sin \alpha \cos \beta + \cos \alpha \sin \beta}{\cos \alpha \cos \beta - \sin \alpha \sin \beta} = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha \cos \beta + \sin \beta}{\cos \beta - \operatorname{tg} \alpha \sin \beta} = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha + \operatorname{tg} \beta}{1 - \operatorname{tg} \alpha \operatorname{tg} \beta}$$

$$4. \operatorname{tg}(\alpha - \beta) = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha - \operatorname{tg} \beta}{1 + \operatorname{tg} \alpha \operatorname{tg} \beta}$$

$$5. \operatorname{ctg}(\alpha + \beta) = \frac{1}{\operatorname{tg}(\alpha + \beta)} = \frac{1 - \operatorname{tg} \alpha \operatorname{tg} \beta}{\operatorname{tg} \alpha + \operatorname{tg} \beta} = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{\operatorname{ctg} \alpha} \cdot \frac{1}{\operatorname{ctg} \beta}}{\frac{1}{\operatorname{ctg} \alpha} + \frac{1}{\operatorname{ctg} \beta}} = \frac{\operatorname{ctg} \alpha \operatorname{ctg} \beta - 1}{\operatorname{ctg} \alpha + \operatorname{ctg} \beta}$$

$$6. \operatorname{ctg}(\alpha - \beta) = \frac{\operatorname{ctg} \alpha \operatorname{ctg} \beta + 1}{\operatorname{ctg} \alpha - \operatorname{ctg} \beta}$$

Ikkalangan burchak trigonometrik funksiyalari

$$1. \sin 2\alpha = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha$$

Isbot: $\sin 2\alpha = \sin(\alpha + \alpha) = \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + \cos \alpha \sin \alpha = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha$

Formula isbotlandi.

$$2. \cos 2\alpha = \cos^2 \alpha - \sin^2 \alpha$$

$$3. \operatorname{tg} 2\alpha = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \alpha}{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha}$$

$$4. \operatorname{ctg} 2\alpha = \frac{\operatorname{ctg}^2 \alpha - 1}{2 \operatorname{ctg} \alpha}$$

$$5. \cos^2 \alpha = \frac{1 + \cos 2\alpha}{2}$$

$$6. \sin^2 \alpha = \frac{1 - \cos 2\alpha}{2}$$

Trigonometrik ko‘paytmani yig‘indiga keltirish:

$$1. \sin \alpha \cos \beta = \frac{1}{2} [\sin(\alpha - \beta) + \sin(\alpha + \beta)]$$

Isbot: $\sin \alpha \cos \beta = \frac{1}{2} [\sin(\alpha - \beta) + \sin(\alpha + \beta)]$

$$+ \begin{cases} \sin(\alpha + \beta) = \sin \alpha \cos \beta + \cos \alpha \sin \beta \\ \sin(\alpha - \beta) = \sin \alpha \cos \beta - \cos \alpha \sin \beta \end{cases}$$

$$\sin(\alpha + \beta) + \sin(\alpha - \beta) = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \beta$$

$$\sin(\alpha + \beta) + \sin(\alpha - \beta) = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \beta = \frac{1}{2} [\sin(\alpha - \beta) + \sin(\alpha + \beta)]$$

$$2. \cos \alpha \cos \beta = \frac{1}{2} [\cos(\alpha - \beta) + \cos(\alpha + \beta)]$$

$$3. \sin \alpha \sin \beta = \frac{1}{2} [\cos(\alpha - \beta) - \cos(\alpha + \beta)]$$

Yig‘indi va ayirmani ko‘paytmaga keltirish:

$$1. \sin \alpha \pm \sin \beta = 2 \cdot \sin \frac{\alpha \pm \beta}{2} \cos \frac{\alpha \pm \beta}{2}$$

$$2. \cos \alpha + \cos \beta = 2 \cdot \cos \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} \cos \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2}$$

$$3. \cos \alpha - \cos \beta = 2 \cdot \sin \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} \sin \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2}$$

Isbot: $\sin \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} \cos \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sin \left(\frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} + \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} - \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{2} (\sin \alpha + \sin \beta)$

$$\Rightarrow [\sin \alpha + \sin \beta = 2 \cdot \sin \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2} \cos \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2}] \Rightarrow \sin \alpha + \sin \beta$$

Trigonometrik funksiya trigonometrik yarim burchak bo‘yicha formula

$$1. \sin \alpha = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2}}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}$$

Isbot: $\sin \alpha = \frac{2 \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} = \frac{\frac{2 \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}}{\frac{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}} = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2}}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}$

$$2. \cos \alpha = \frac{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}$$

$$3. \operatorname{tg} \alpha = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2}}{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}$$

Yuqoridagi keltirilgan formulalarga doir ba'zi namunaviy misollar ko'ramiz.

1-masala. Ifodani soddalashtiring: $\cos^2 \alpha - 1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha * \cos^2 \alpha$

Yechim:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos^2 \alpha - 1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha * \cos^2 \alpha &= \cos^2 \alpha - \sin^2 \alpha - \cos^2 \alpha + \frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{\cos^2 \alpha} * \cos^2 \alpha = \\ -\sin^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

2-masala. Ifodani soddalashtiring: $\cos x * \operatorname{tg} x + \cos x * \operatorname{ctg} x$

Yechim:

$$\cos x * \operatorname{tg} x + \cos x * \operatorname{ctg} x = \cos x * \frac{\sin x}{\cos x} + \cos x * \frac{\cos x}{\sin x} = \sin x + \frac{\cos^2 x}{\sin x} = \frac{1}{\sin x}$$

3-masala. $\frac{\cos 2\alpha}{\cos \alpha - \sin \alpha}$ ning qiymatini hisoblang.

Yechim:

$$\frac{\cos 2\alpha}{\cos \alpha - \sin \alpha} = \frac{\cos^2 \alpha - \sin^2 \alpha}{\cos \alpha - \sin \alpha} = \frac{(\cos \alpha - \sin \alpha)(\cos \alpha + \sin \alpha)}{\cos \alpha - \sin \alpha} = \cos \alpha + \sin \alpha$$

4-masala. $\sin x = \frac{1}{4}$ berilgan bo'lsa, $\cos 5x * \cos 7x + \sin 5x * \sin 7x$ ni hisoblang.

Yechim:

$\cos 5x * \cos 7x + \sin 5x * \sin 7x = \cos(7x - 5x) = \cos 2x$; $\sin x = \frac{1}{4}$ masala shartidan foydalanamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 2x &= \cos^2 x - \sin^2 x = 1 - \sin^2 x - \sin^2 x = 1 - 2\sin^2 x = 1 - 2 * \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 = \\ &= 1 - \frac{2}{16} = \frac{7}{8} \end{aligned}$$

5-masala. Ifodani soddalashtiring: $\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha\right) + \sin(\pi - \alpha)$

Yechim:

$$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha\right) + \sin(\pi - \alpha) = -\sin \alpha + \sin \alpha = 0$$

6-masala. Ifodani soddalashtiring: $\frac{\cos(\alpha+\beta)+2 \sin \alpha \cos \beta}{\cos(\alpha-\beta)}$

Yechim:

$$\frac{\cos(\alpha + \beta) + 2 \sin \alpha \cos \beta}{\cos(\alpha - \beta)} = \frac{\cos \alpha \cos \beta - \sin \alpha \sin \beta + 2 \sin \alpha \sin \beta}{\cos \alpha \cos \beta + \sin \alpha \sin \beta} = 1$$

7-masala. Ifodaning eng kichik qiymatini hisoblang: $2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \operatorname{tg} \alpha + 1$

Yechim:

$$2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \operatorname{tg} \alpha + 1 = 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha} + \cos^2 \alpha + \sin^2 \alpha = \cos^2 \alpha + 3 \sin^2 \alpha =$$

$$1, \alpha = \pi k$$

8-masala. Ifodaning eng katta qiymatini hisoblang: $3 - 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \operatorname{ctg} \alpha$

Yechim:

$$3 - 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \operatorname{ctg} \alpha = 3 \cos^2 \alpha + 3 \sin^2 \alpha - 2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha} = \cos^2 \alpha + 3 \sin^2 \alpha = 1 + 2 \cos^2 \alpha = 3, \alpha = \pi k$$

9-masala: $\operatorname{ctg}\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \alpha\right) + \operatorname{ctg} x = 5$ tenglik o'rinli bo'lsa, u holda $\operatorname{tg}^2 x + \operatorname{ctg}^2 x$ ning qiymatini toping.

Yechim:

$$(-\operatorname{tg} x + \operatorname{ctg} x)^2 = 5^2$$

$$\operatorname{tg}^2 x - 2 \operatorname{tg} x \operatorname{ctg} x + \operatorname{ctg}^2 x = 25$$

$$\operatorname{tg}^2 x - 2 + \operatorname{ctg}^2 x = 25$$

$$\operatorname{tg}^2 x + \operatorname{ctg}^2 x = 27$$

10-masala. Ifodaning qiymatini hisoblang: $\frac{\sin^4 \alpha + \cos^4 \alpha - 1}{\sin^6 \alpha + \cos^6 \alpha - 1}$

Yechim:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\sin^4\alpha + \cos^4\alpha - 1}{\sin^6\alpha + \cos^6\alpha - 1} &= \frac{\sin^4\alpha + \cos^4\alpha - \sin^2\alpha - \cos^2\alpha}{\sin^6\alpha + \cos^6\alpha - \sin^2\alpha - \cos^2\alpha} = \\
 &= \frac{\sin^2\alpha(-1 + \sin^2\alpha) + \cos^2\alpha(\cos^2\alpha - 1)}{\sin^2\alpha(\sin^4\alpha - 1) + \cos^2\alpha(\cos^4\alpha - 1)} = \\
 &= \frac{-\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha - \cos^2\alpha\sin^2\alpha}{\sin^2\alpha(\sin^4\alpha - \sin^2\alpha - \cos^2\alpha) + \cos^2\alpha(\cos^4\alpha - \cos^2\alpha - \sin^2\alpha)} = \\
 &= \frac{-2\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha}{\sin^2\alpha(\sin^2\alpha(\sin^2\alpha - 1) - \cos^2\alpha) + \cos^2\alpha(\cos^2\alpha(\cos^2\alpha - 1) - \sin^2\alpha)} = \\
 &= \frac{-2\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha}{\sin^2\alpha(-\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha - \cos^2\alpha) + \cos^2\alpha(-\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha - \sin^2\alpha)} = \\
 &= \frac{-2\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha}{-\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha(\sin^2\alpha + 1) - \sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha(\cos^2\alpha + 1)} = \\
 &= \frac{-2\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha}{-\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha(\sin^2\alpha + \cos^2\alpha + 2)} = \frac{2}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

11-masala. Ifodani soddalashtiring: $\sin^3 2\alpha \cos 6\alpha + \cos^6 \alpha \sin 6\alpha$

Yechim:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sin^3 2\alpha \cos 6\alpha + \cos^6 \alpha \sin 6\alpha &= (\sin 2\alpha)^3 \cos 2 \cdot 3\alpha + (\cos 2\alpha)^3 \sin 2 \cdot 3\alpha \\
 &= \sin 2\alpha \cos 2\alpha ((\sin 2\alpha)^2 \cos 2 \cdot 2\alpha + (\cos 2\alpha)^2 \sin 2 \cdot 2\alpha) = \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sin 4\alpha (\sin 2\alpha \cos 2\alpha (\sin 2\alpha \cos 2\alpha + \sin 2\alpha \cos 2\alpha)) = \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sin 4\alpha (\cos 2\alpha \sin 4\alpha) = \frac{1}{4} \sin 4\alpha \cdot \sin 4\alpha \cdot \sin 4\alpha = \frac{1}{4} \sin^3 4\alpha
 \end{aligned}$$

Yuqorida keltirilib o‘tilgan namunaviy masalalar maktab o‘quvchilari va oliy ta’lim muassasalari talabalari uchun trigonometrik funksiyalar va ularni ayniy almashtirish borasida elementar tushunchalarni paydo qilishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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